

Design, Analysis and Testing of Two Concepts for a Dimensional Stable Structure

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials are well suited for structural applications which require high dimensional stability when exposed to various environmental conditions, like an antenna tower of a communications satellite.

This paper describes the design, analysis and structural as well as environmental testing of two different antenna tower truss concepts. The antenna tower structure consists of four axially main tubes and two equipment platforms. The connection between the longitudinal tubes - which is the subject of this investigation - can be verified either by lateral and diagonal tubes or by a shear panel. The thermal performance of the structures was tested in a thermal-vacuum environment by using the laser holographic interferometry measurement technique. In a static test the load of fracture, the mode of failure and the structural stiffness of both antenna tower trusses were determined.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials, by virtue of their low coefficient of thermal expansion and high strength and stiffness to weight ratios, are becoming increasingly important for spacecraft structural applications, which have to fulfill high dimensional stability requirements under various environmental conditions.

A typical example of such a kind of spacecraft structure is an antenna tower of a communications satellite, which has to provide the attachment of various feeds, reflectors and sensors of the antenna system and which has to guarantee the exact alignment of the system during the life of the satellite. The antenna tower as shown in figure 1 is constructed of four axially main tubes and an upper and lower equipment platform, where feeds and antennas are attached. Lateral stiffness and load transfer may be provided either by lateral and diagonal tubes or by a shear panel between the main tubes. The purpose of the investigation, which is presented here, was to study the mechanical and thermal performance of these two different design concepts of an antenna tower structure.

Besides the advantages, i.e. low CTE and high relative strength and stiffness, composite materials show some remarkable disadvantages concerning structural long-term stability, i.e. the hygroscopic nature and the viscoelastic behavior of the epoxy resin matrix commonly used for fibre composites. The influ-

ence of moisture and creep especially at elevated temperatures has to be considered in the long-term stability performance of precision structures during service life. Thus the design of a precision structure, such as the antenna tower, according to structural, thermal and communications design requirements is not necessarily an optimum in terms of long-term stability. With this in mind the following discussion of the mechanical and thermal performance and the evaluation of the two antenna tower structure concepts was prepared.

DESIGN

Each of the two structural concepts simulates a subsystem of the total antenna tower. Both antenna tower models consist of two main tubes, each with an inner diameter of 46 mm and a wall thickness of 1.6 mm manufactured by filament winding of M40 carbon fibres impregnated with an epoxy resin and cured at 120°C. The two tubes are connected with a top and a bottom sandwich panel with GY70 carbon fibre quasi-isotropic face-sheets and an aluminum honeycomb core with 20 mm height. The tubes are set at an angle of 5° to the vertical axis and the distance of the tube axes is 355 mm at the bottom panel and 250 mm at the top panel. The sandwich panels have a mutual distance of 600 mm. Within that frame, shaped as a parallelogram, the two different design concepts for lateral load transfer are developed.

Shear panel solution

The shear panel antenna tower substructure is shown in figure 2. The construction utilizes GY70 carbon fibre prepreg face sheets and an aluminum honeycomb core. Due to the shear loading the face sheets should have a +/- 45° lay-up. This however, would lead to problems due to stress concentration at the free edges of the two cut-outs of the shear panel. Therefore a quasi-isotropic lay-up with (0°, +/- 60°) was chosen for the face sheet design. With the ultrathin GY70 prepreg (60 micr. ply-thickness) a honeycomb core with 16 kg/m³ and an adhesive film with 100 g/m² for the face sheet bonding the total area weight of the sandwich panel summarizes to 1720 g/m² for a core height of 5 mm. Critical item in the design of that shear panel solution is the connection of the panel with the axially main tubes of the tower. The connection is designed as an adhesive bonding via angle profiles made of CFRP. In the real stress distribution in the adhesive bond, peak stresses in shear and peel occur at the edges, which try to loosen the bonded profiles by a bending moment action. The lateral shear stiffness of the antenna tower depends strongly on that weak link of the adhesively bonded profiles.

The overall thermal expansion behavior of the shear panel solution is mainly influenced by the coefficient of thermal expansion of the sandwich panel itself. Due to the anisotropy of the honeycomb core the CTE of the sandwich will be anisotropically too, but with an appropriate design of the face sheets the CTE of the overall sandwich may be adjusted to an quasi-isotropic behavior. To avoid a 'bimetal-effect' the CTE of the connection profiles has to be adjusted to those of the main tubes. Due to the lay-out of the main tubes and the anisotropic material behavior this adjustment may only be verified in axial direction of the main tubes but not in circumferential direction.

Tubular framework solution

The tubular framework design concept of the antenna tower substructure is shown in figure 3. The main tubes of the tower as well as the lateral and diagonal tubes are slotted and mutually attached to one another by adhesively bonded node plates and profile clips. All tubes are manufactured by filament winding of epoxy resin impregnated M40 carbon fibres and are cured at 120°C. To avoid bending moment action at the nodes the axes of the tubes are centered at one point on the main tube axes. The critical item in the lateral load transfer in this design concept is the node plate, where shear forces are introduced and distributed via interlaminar shear in the node plate. As it is well known the interlaminar shear strength mainly depends on the type of fibre material and the laminate ply angles. The interlaminar shear strength of high-tensile fibres is higher than that of high-modulus and ultra-high-modulus carbon fibre lami-

nates with the same laminate geometry. On the other hand the design of the antenna tower structure is restrained by the lateral thermal expansion behavior which is mainly influenced by the node plates. In contrast to the interlaminar shear strength the ultra-high-modulus fibres provide the lowest CTE while the high-tensile fibre composites have the highest CTE. Thus the final design for tubular framework solution utilizes high-modulus fibre composite node plates as a compromise.

TESTING

Thermal expansion test

The thermal performance of the structures was tested in a thermal-vacuum environment by using the laser holographic interferometry measurement technique which is described in more detail in (1). By a quantitative evaluation of three holograms taken from three different directions of illumination you get the spatial thermal distortion of the total structure. The CTE-measurement set-up is shown in figure 4. The thermal expansion measurements were performed under a plexiglass-dome. The test-article was stored under vacuum for 72 h prior to the testing to allow a moisture desorption of the material. Then the test-article was heated up to appr. 10°C above room-temperature. During the following cool-down phase the holograms were taken with a temperature difference of appr. -1.5°C to -4.0°C . The temperature difference depends on the amount of thermal distortion which is expected to appear on the test-article. The accuracy obtained with this measurement method expressed in terms of the coefficient of thermal expansion is $\pm 0.05 \cdot 10^{-6}/\text{K}$.

The results of the thermal expansion test for the shear panel concept may be summarized as follows: The sandwich panel strips bonded to the tubes to simulate the spatial connection of the shear panels of the total tower cause an axial bending of the main tubes. At the top and bottom sandwich plate the shear panel shows a curvature in lateral direction. The structural coefficients of thermal expansion of the main elements of the shear panel concept are:

CTE left tube axial	=	-0.55	$10.0\text{E}-06$	1/K
CTE right tube axial	=	-0.62	$10.0\text{E}-06$	1/K
CTE shear panel	=	+1.30	$10.0\text{E}-06$	1/K

A hologram of the shear panel structure is shown in figure 5.

The results of the thermal expansion test of the tubular framework solution may be summarized as follows: Axial thermal expansion of the main tubes is disturbed locally, which might be caused by the slots. There is a lateral bending of the main tubes observed, which is due to the higher CTE of the top and bottom sandwich plates compared to the lateral connection tube. The diagonal tubes also show a local disturbance in the axial expansion behavior and a bending out of the plane of the framework. The structural coefficients of thermal expansion of the tubes of the framework concept are:

CTE main tubes axial	=	-0.71	$10.0\text{E}-06$	1/K
CTE diagonal tubes	=	-0.73	$10.0\text{E}-06$	1/K

A hologram of the framework structure is shown in figure 6.

Static load test

In a static load test the load to fracture, the mode of failure and the structural stiffness of both antenna tower trusses were determined. The load was introduced into the structure in lateral direction at the upper sandwich plate in the plane of the truss. The structures were supported at the bottom of the main tubes. Support fittings and load introduction elements of the structures are to be seen in figures 2 and 3.

The shear panel structure failed in the sandwich skin laminate of the shear panel at a load of 11800 N. The maximum shear stress, which initiated the failure, occurred at the edge of the upper cutout of the shear panel. The failed structure is shown in figure 7.

The tubular framework structure failed at a load of 9500 N in the joint-plate of the upper sandwich platform. Secondary failure occurred in the joint-plate of the lateral and diagonal tubes which is shown in figure 8.

ANALYSIS

For the prediction of structural response due to thermal and static loading finite-element models of both structures were established utilizing the SAP V computer program (2). Beam and membrane elements were used to model the structures. The maximum deformation measured during the static load test occurred at the upper end of the main tubes in direction of the introduced load. The following table gives a comparison of predicted and measured deformations for both structures at a load of 8000 N.

structure	max. deformation (mm)		stiffness (N/mm)	
	analysis	test	analysis	test
shear panel	1.36	1.64	5880	4880
framework	1.57	1.78	5095	4500

The lateral stiffness, i.e. load per deformation, of the shear panel structure is predicted to be 15 % higher than the stiffness of the framework concept. Test results showed a 8 % higher stiffness of the shear panel solution. In both cases analysis overestimated the stiffness of the structures. In a subsequent laminate analysis as described in (3) utilizing the concepts of single layer stress analysis and linear elastic laminate theory a detailed investigation of the laminate failure of both structures was performed. The failure stresses obtained by this analysis clearly identified the sites of failure in both structures.

Results of a thermal expansion analysis for both structures agreed very well with the measured thermal expansion behavior described above. The lateral bending of the shear panel and the resulting bending of the main tubes could be verified by analysis as well as the structural coefficient of thermal expansion of $1.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$ 1/K of the shear panel. The thermal analysis of the framework structure showed that the structural CTE of the main tubes in axial direction is equal to the CTE of the tube material itself and that the positive CTE of the joint-plates could be compensated by the negative CTE of the lateral tube.

CONCLUSION

An evaluation of the two structural concepts for an antenna tower is given in the following table. The plus-sign indicates the structural concept with the better performance with respect to the corresponding criterion.

criterion	shear panel concept	framework concept
mass	-	+
manufacturing costs	+	-
material costs	-	+
component mounting	-	+
tools	-	+
number of parts	+	-
stiffness	+	-
thermal stability	-	+
optimization possibility	-	+
analytical modelling	-	+

Main criteria for recommending the tubular framework concept for the design of a communications satellite antenna tower is the lower mass and the higher thermal stability compared with the shear panel solution. Higher manufacturing costs are compensated by lower material costs and a less number of necessary tools for final assembly. The main disadvantage of the shear panel concept, i.e. the high CTE of the aluminum honeycomb sandwich of the panel, can be eliminated by utilizing another core material with a lower CTE.

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Figure 1: Antenna Tower of a Communications Satellite

Figure 2: Shear Panel Antenna Tower Substructure

Figure 3: Tubular Framework Antenna Tower Substructure

Figure 4: CTE-Measurement Set-up

Figure 5: Hologram of the Shear Panel Structure

Figure 6: Hologram of the Framework Structure

Figure 7: Failed Shear Panel Structure

Figure 8: Failed Joint of the Framework Structure

